

THE EVALUATION OF THE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS PATRIOTISM LEVELS ACCORDING TO GENDER, AGE, FAMILY STRUCTURE AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

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Abstract:

The degree of an individual patriotism is expected to influence his social duty performance and responsibility. So, it is a requirement to determine the factors effective on patriotism. So 555 students (F=307 n, M=248 n; M= 21 yrs) from Atatürk University participated in this study. Patriotism Attitude Scale (PAS) developed by Yazıcı (2010) was used to obtain the data. Data was analysed by In-dependent T test and one way ANOVA at P=0.05 level. The results showed that there is a significantly difference between gender, family structure and performance level of sportive activities and the degree of patriotism attitude. There was not significantly difference between age and patriotism. The means of constructive patriotism (CP), subscale of PAS, among sport performing students are higher than sedentary subjects. Performance of sport activities has favourable effects on patriotism level. Sport activities have positive effects on the physical, social and cognitive development of students

Keywords: patriotism, sports activities, family structure

1. Introduction

Patriotism has always been the conflicting point of liberal congregant politic philosophers. Some congregant thinkers define patriotism as a virtue, responsibility or necessity while some of liberal thinkers bear the view relying on universal justice principle that patriotism is not the representative of moral values (Yazıcı, 2009).

Fiedrich Ludwing, founder of gymnastic school in Germany (1811-1819), stated that sports (gymnastics) are not simply a physical activity but also a tool to contribute to

the free education and patriot people. Such a thought was spread from Germany to whole Europe (Mirzeoğlu, 2014).

Patriotism has two main aspects. Blind patriotism represents a dependence type requiring the adoption of policies and activities of the country where patriot lives without questioning and is characterised by an unquestioned loyalty (Schatz, et al., 1999). Constructive patriotism requires people to dismiss the society's policies and activities when they witness a condition where people betray basic principles of society and principle humanistic values (Schatz, et al., 1999). Social psychologists evaluate patriotism in the scope of individuals' relationship with society. According to the most common definition, patriotism can be defined to be the dependence of group members on their own territory (Bar-Tal and Staub, 1997).

Patriotism is individuals' sense of closeness towards his/her nation. Such a sense is the combination of past experiences, present perception and expectation from future (Ben, 2007). In Ottoman policy, a patriotic understanding tried to be constructed among different ethnical and religion groups in order to increase the common shares and wishes to live together. Namık Kemal proposed an education system open to everyone by advocating that the political rights of all people should be guaranteed in order to realize a union. According to Kemal, such a union can best be improved by people sitting at the same desk side by side (Mardin, 2008). It can be stated that increased patriotism level of societies and individuals are the important factor for the development of both individuals and societies. Individuals will gain the opportunity to develop themselves from every aspect in a patriotism consciousness by supplying benefits to them, society and homeland.

Sport has psychological–social effects on individuals and societies. Such effects include love, share, claim deserved rights, being fair, race and competence, obey the rules, accepting results from winning or losing, participating in new social media and setting up new friendships and taking pleasure (Doğan, 2004). Sport is an effective factor on the formation of individual characteristics and socialisation process. Therefore, sports may contribute to an individual in social harmonisation and ensure psychological and physical development of people. Sportive activities are not only the physical occupations but also socialisation and harmonisation to social environment (Fişe, 1980; Karasüleymanoğlu, 1989; Öztürk, 1983; Marris and and Ross, 1976).

Positive mental, psychological and physical effects of sports may have benefits for themselves and society (Tozoğlu et al., 2013). Sport is effective on the development of individual and social relationships and plays important roles in the improvement of the characteristics of society. Sports also helps individuals behave in harmony with society and secure their psychological and physical health (Yetim, 2014). It can be seen

in the light of definitions and expressions that consciousness of patriotism is an important component in the development of individuals and societies. It is thought that it has favourable effects on individuals and societies. Also, sports may positively affect patriotism sense of people.

The aim of present study is to investigate the effect of the variables of gender, age, family structure and sports on patriotism attitude level (PAL) among Faculty Education students of Atatürk University.

Materials and Method

PAS is composed of 20 items, however item 13 was removed from the scale after the validity and confidence test leaving 19 items behind in the study. The scale (PAS), which is five – point Likert type scale, determined participants' responses (justice) to be "I absolutely disagree" (1), I disagree (2), I am unstable (3), I agree (4), I absolutely, agree (5). The scale includes 2 subscales; blind patriotism (1.2.3.4.5.6.7.8.9.10.11.12) and constructive patriotism (14.15.16.17.18.19). The reliability of the scale was 0.76 and 0.77 for blind patriotism and constructive patriotism. 555 university students (F=307 n, M=248 n; M=21 yrs) from Atatürk University participated in the study. Data obtained by PAS were analysed by SPSS version 21 and Independent T-test, variance analysis and one way ANOVA. Within consistency coefficients of the scale were found to be 0.80 and 0.90 for blind patriotism and constructive patriotism respectively, while 0.88 was for whole scale.

Results

Table 1 represents demographic characteristics of participants and Table 2 gives the frequency distributions of their sportive activity performance level. Table 3, 6 and 7 present the results of Independent T test conducted for the determination of the relationship of the values obtained from PAS with the variables of gender, sportive activity and the type of sportive activity. Statistical results of one way ANOVA analysis are given in Table 4, 5, 8 and related to the variables of age, family structure, the time of sport activity in a week and the reason for starting sport.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants

Demographic characteristics		N	%
Gender	Female	307	55.3
	Male	248	44.7
	Total	555	100.0
Age group	19 and below	47	8.5
	20 to 22	294	53.0
	23 and above	214	38.6
Marital status	Married	27	4.9
	Single	528	95.1
Family structure	Core family	432	77.8
	Big family	109	19.6
	Broken family	14	2.5
Monthly income	Minimum wage and below	371	66.8
	1000-2000 TL	121	21.8
	2001-3000 TL	49	8.8
	3001 and above	14	2.5

Table 2: Sportive performance of the participants

Sportive performance		N	%
Do you perform a sportive activity?	Yes	311	56.0
	No	244	44.0
	Total	555	100.0
Type of sportive activity	Collective	168	30.3
	Individual	142	25.6
	I perform no sportive activity.	245	44.1
How many hours do you perform a sportive activity a week?	1 hour and shorter	45	8.1
	2 to 4 hours	113	20.4
	5 to 7 hours	76	13.7
	8 hours and longer	77	13.9
	Never	244	44.0
Reason to start sports	Family's wish	35	6.3
	Individual's wish	260	46.8
	Social media	16	2.9
	I perform no sportive activity	244	44.0

Table 3: Mean and SD of participants' scores received for subscales of PAS

Patriotism attitude level	Gender	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	Female	307	41.89	7.655	1.96	.000
	Male	248	40.35	10.80	1.89	
Blind patriotism	Female	307	30.13	4.533	4.26	.000
	Male	248	27.90	7.623	4.05	

As Table 3 shows there is a statistically significant difference between gender and the mean score of the subscale of PAS. Mean scores of female students received for the subscales of constructive patriotism and blind patriotism are higher than male students.

Table 4: Mean One way ANOVA

Patriotism attitude level	Age	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	19 and below	47	41.23	6.68	1.570	.077
	20 to 22	294	40.58	8.81		
	23 and above	214	42.05	10.16		
	Total	555	41.20	9.22		
Blind patriotism	19 and below	47	29.55	4.73	.681	.507
	20 to 22	294	28.85	6.35		
	23 and above	214	29.44	6.28		
	Total	555	29.13	6.20		

As Table 4 shows there is no significantly significant difference between age and the mean score of the subscale of PAS. However, mean scores of students in the age groups of 23 and above are higher than other groups.

Table 5: Mean scores and SD of students with different family structures for subscales of PAS

Patriotism attitude level	Family structure	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	Core family	432	41.7	8.68	3.643	.001
	Big family	109	39.14	11.01		
	Broken family	14	40.07	8.25		
	Total	555	41.20	9.22		
Blind patriotism	Core family	432	29.67	5.42	7.345	.000
	Big family	109	27.26	8.35		
	Broken family	14	27.28	6.50		
	Total	555	29.13	6.20		

As Table 5 shows, there is a significantly difference between family structure and the mean score of the subscale of PAS. Mean scores of students with core family were found to be higher than those with other two family structures in both constructive patriotism and blind patriotism.

Table 6: Mean and SD of participants' scores performing and not performing sports

Patriotism attitude level	Performance of sports	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	Yes	311	42.54	9.071	3.91	.000
	No	244	39.49	9.144	3.48	
Blind patriotism	Yes	311	29.40	5.978	.930	.248
	No	244	28.79	6.477	1.456	

As Table 6 shows there is a significantly difference between sport performance and the mean score of the constructive patriotism, subscale of PA. Mean scores of students performing sportive activities were found to be higher than those not. However, there was no significantly difference between mean scores of blind patriotism.

Table 7: Mean and SD of participants' scores performing individual and collective sports

Patriotism attitude level	Type of sportive activity	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	Collective	168	43.11	10.36	1.262	.001
	Individual	142	41.80	7.215	1.299	
Blind patriotism	Collective	168	28.60	6.776	-2.559	.001
	Individual	142	30.33	4.733	-2.634	

As Table 7 shows, there is a significantly difference between the types of sports and the mean score of the constructive patriotism, subscale of PAS. Students performing collective sportive activities were found to receive higher mean scores of constructive patriotism than those performing individual activities. However, mean scores of the students performing individual sports were found to be higher than those performing individual sports in blind patriotism.

Table 8: Mean and SD of participants' scores received for weekly sport time and subscales of PAS

Patriotism attitude level	Weekly time for sports	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	1 hour and shorter	45	40.11	7.37	5.800	.000
	2 to 4 hours	113	44.22	8.62		
	5 to 7 hours	76	41.78	11.60		
	8 hours and above	77	42.25	7.28		
	Not performing sports	244	39.49	9.14		
	Total	555	41.20	9.22		
Blind patriotism	1 hour and shorter	45	27.91	5.84	1.749	.138
	2 to 4 hours	113	30.28	5.16		
	5 to 7 hours	76	28.81	7.87		
	8 hours and above	77	29.58	4.75		
	Not performing sports	244	28.79	6.47		
	Total	555	29.13	6.20		

As Table 8 shows, there is significantly difference between length of the weekly time students spend for sports and the mean score of the constructive patriotism, subscale of PAS. Students performing sportive activities for 2 to 4 hours weekly were found to receive higher mean scores than those others and sedentary ones.

Table 9: Mean and SD of participants' scores students received for the reason of starting sports

Patriotism attitude level	Reason for starting sports	N	X	SD	T	P
Constructive patriotism	Family's wish	35	47.65	7.92	10.394	.000
	My wish	260	41.67	9.01		
	Social media	16	45.50	8.46		
	Not performing sports	244	39.49	9.14		
	Total	555	41.20	9.22		
Blind patriotism	Family's wish	35	30.94	3.62	1.521	.000
	My wish	260	29.13	6.30		
	Social media	16	30.56	3.68		
	Not performing sports	244	28.79	6.47		
	Total	555	29.13	6.20		

As Table 9 shows, there is significantly difference between the reasons of starting sports and the mean score of the subscales of PAS. Students starting sports due to their families were found to receive higher mean scores in constructive patriotism and blind patriotism than those starting by themselves, social media and not performing sports.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to find relationship between sportive habits, demographic characteristics and patriotism attitudes of university students. It was determined that the mean PAS scores of female and male students were different at the significance level of $P=0.05$. Mean scores of female students received for the subscales of constructive patriotism and blind patriotism are higher than male students.

Mousavi and Roshan (2010) stated patriotic identity differentiated in favour of females whereas Lay and Purta (2001) reported males are more patriotic in USA and Russia. Tartakovsky (2010) concluded males' sense more powerful identity towards their country (Mousavi, Androshan, 2010, Lay and Purta, 2001, Tartakovsky, 2010). There was no-statistically significant difference between age and the mean score of the subscale of PAS. Mean scores of students in the age groups of 23 and above were determined to be higher than those in the groups of 19 and below and 20 to 22. There was significantly difference between family structure and the mean score of the subscale of PAS. Mean scores of students with core family were found to be higher than with two family structures in both constructive patriotism and blind patriotism. There was significantly difference between the students' performance of sportive activities and the mean score of the constructive patriotism, subscale of PAS.

The students performing sportive activities were found to receive higher PAS scores than sedentary ones. There was significantly difference between the types of sports (collective and individual) and the mean subscale scores of PAS. Students performing collective sportive activities were found to receive higher mean scores of constructive patriotism than those performing individual activities. However, mean scores of the students performing individual sports were found to be higher than those performing individual sports in blind patriotism. There was significantly difference between the length of the weekly time spending for sports and the mean score of the constructive patriotism. Students performing sportive activities for 2 to 4 hours weekly were found to receive higher mean scores than others and sedentary ones. It was reported that there is significantly difference between the reasons of start sport by participants and the subscale of patriotism attitude. There was significantly difference between the reasons of starting sports and the mean score of the subscales of PAS.

Students starting sports due to their families were found to receive higher mean scores in constructive patriotism and blind patriotism than those starting by themselves, social media and sedentary ones. According to Yetim (2014), the aim of sport is to develop individuals and society morally and socially, enable them to perceive at the highest level the concepts of nation and motherland and bring up

individuals who are aware of their responsibility against society, have common sense and adopt the concept of national unity (Yetim, 2014). Similar and supporting results with the mentioned ones can also be seen in the present study implying that the individuals performing sportive activities reflect the sense of patriotism at higher levels. It may be suggested when favourable effects of sportive activities on university students' level of patriotism are considered that students should be encouraged to perform sportive activities in their educational processes. It is vitally important to determine different variables thought to be effective on patriotism and carry out different studies to make contributions to the development of societies.

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